

PEDAGOGICAL INNOVATION

Mamatkulova Gulandon Rustamjon kyzy

Kochkarova Gulnoza Shavkiddin kyzy

Scientific adviser: Gasanova Nasiba Shavkievna

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Annotation: The article discusses the concept of innovation and its types, innovative activities. Particular attention is paid to the perception of innovation as a category that has a specific meaning and a specific result.

Keywords: innovative activity, personality, idea, method.

Today, the main purpose of training is not only the accumulation of a certain amount of knowledge, skills, but also the preparation of the student as an independent subject of educational activity. The basis of modern education is activity and the teacher, and, no less important, the student. It is this goal - the upbringing of a creative, active person who knows how to learn, improve independently, and the main tasks of modern education are subordinated.

What is "innovative learning" and what are its features?

Today, many changes are taking place in society, and the modern child needs to keep up with these changes. A traditional teacher (a monopolist in the transfer of necessary knowledge) leaves the stage. He is being replaced by a teacher-researcher, educator, consultant, project manager, teacher with an innovative style of thinking, capable of creative and professional activity, self-determination and self-development. Such a teacher positively affects the quality of education and upbringing in an educational institution, creates the conditions for the spiritual development of children, and implements a personality-oriented approach to them.

Innovation is the introduction of a new goal, content, methods and forms of training and education, the organization of joint activities of a teacher and student.

Pedagogical innovation - an innovation in pedagogical activity, changes in the content and technology of training and education aimed at increasing their effectiveness.

The definition of "innovation" as a pedagogical criterion is common and comes down, as a rule, to the concept of "innovation", "novelty." Meanwhile, innovation in the exact translation from the Latin language does not mean "new", but "into new".

On the one hand, the development of society, man, all aspects of his activity has always been associated with the emergence of new ideas, innovations, i.e. with innovation. The constant historical, political and socio-economic changes taking place in society revealed new requirements for society and man. It was they who formed the social order, in particular, in the field of education. And socially demanded innovations, innovations have always been, so to speak, the answer to a social order. Therefore, the very concept of "innovation", as it does not seem paradoxical, is not innovative. However, on the other hand, such an increased interest in innovation in all areas of society means, apparently, a special need for innovation today. This is clearly evident in the field of education.

In pedagogical science, innovative activity is understood as focused pedagogical activity, based on the reflection (reflection) of one's own practical experience by comparing and studying, changing and developing the educational process in order to achieve better results, to obtain new knowledge, and a completely different pedagogical practice. We think that innovations in education, first of all, should be aimed at creating a personality that is set up for success in any area of application of its capabilities. By readiness for innovative activity, we understand the totality of the qualities of a teacher that determine his focus on improving his own pedagogical activity and the activities of the entire team of educational institutions, as well as his ability to identify current problems of education, find and implement effective ways to solve them. The main goal of innovative activity is the development of a teacher as a creative person, switching from a reproductive type of activity to an independent search for met period solutions, turning the teacher into a developer and author of innovative techniques and implement their learning tools, development and education.

Literature

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